

ABOUT TEACHING SPEAKING**Tursunboyeva Latofat Tukhtamuradovna****Djalilova Sabokhat Rihsibayevna****Kazoqov Ruxilla Turopovich**

Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sport.

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Abstract. *What steps are involved in speaking? Think about conversation that you have with your friends or family. What do you do before you say something? When we talk our friend in our native language our brains think quickly and easily. We don't notice that speaking is very complicated. However when we speak a foreign language, it takes us much longer to talk. This is because speaking is composed of many steps.*

Key words: *communication, speaking activities, vocabulary, pronounce, conversation, interviewing, chatting, language.*

ОБ ОБУЧЕНИИ ГОВОРЯЩЕЙ РЕЧИ

Аннотация. *Какие этапы включает в себя говорение? Подумайте о разговоре, который вы ведете с друзьями или семьей. Что вы делаете, прежде чем что-то сказать? Когда мы разговариваем с другом на родном языке, наш мозг думает быстро и легко. Мы не замечаем, что говорение очень сложно. Однако, когда мы говорим на иностранном языке, нам требуется гораздо больше времени, чтобы заговорить. Это потому, что говорение состоит из многих этапов.*

Ключевые слова: *общение, речевая деятельность, словарный запас, произнесение, разговор, интервьюирование, чат, язык.*

To speak we do the following:

1. Listen and understand other people.
2. Have an idea and want to express it.
3. Remember vocabulary which can express this idea.
4. Use grammar correctly.
5. Pronounce the words understandably.

Speaking is an active skill. Speakers think of everything themselves, the ideas, the words, the grammar. Finally all of the words and grammar must be pronounced clearly. This is much more difficult than listening. No wonder speaking English is so difficult, Using recitation to practice

speaking is wrong. It doesn't practice the skills students will need to speak English fluently. When students practice speaking in the classroom, they should do the steps which are part of speaking.

They need to think of original ideas, remember words and use grammar themselves.

Speaking which resemble real communication prepare students better for speaking outside in the classroom. How to create real speaking in the classroom. Even if teachers are ready to practice speaking the lessons will not be successful unless the students themselves want to talk.

But how can teachers make students want to talk. We need to choose interesting, useful and fun themes for our lessons. Remember that students love to talk about themselves and their opinions, their hobbies and their families. Students like to play games in English. They also enjoy using their imagination to create situations. What would they say on an English singers or actors or the president of America? The best speaking activities have one or more of these elements an opportunity for students to talk about themselves, a chance to use English as a game, or a time to fantasize about a story or situation.

Good speaking activities also resemble real world conversations. They require students to find out information by asking questions and listening to the answers. In this way they communicate with their groupmates and you their teacher. Students use English to describe a situation which has meaning for them. This shows students the context for words. Thus they learn that a word is more than letters on paper, it has a meaning and other words associated with it.

Using words within a context helps students remember vocabulary and use words correctly.

Communicative speaking activities often have tasks which make students talk about themselves, their ideas, or a situation within the classroom. There are three main kinds of communicative activities: opinion gap activities, information gap activities and guessing games.

Within these activities, someone has information which other students need to complete a task. This situation creates "communicative need". Communicative need means students have a reason to communicate with each other. Students listen and speak to each other to complete the task successfully. Students exchange personal information about themselves in opinion gap activities. They interview each other using words which they are learning in class. For example if your class is learning about professions they can discuss their family jobs. While interview each other they fill in a chart. After they are finished interviewing their partner you discuss the answers.

Students who are good at English can also use it by taking more difficult topics. Students exchange information about other topic in information gap activities. In these activities one student has information that the other student needs. For example half of the students are given a piece of paper with information. The students in the other group should interview them and by this way they can learn their information. When they are finished asking questions they may look at the

paper to see if their answers are correct. Guessing games are the most interesting communicative activities for students. In these games students guess the answer to a puzzle. The teacher writes some names which are interesting for students to pieces of paper and puts them on his table. The papers are face-down so students cannot see the words. One student comes to the front, chooses a paper, but keeps the name of the word a secret. Student describes the word and others try to guess it. Students often make mistakes when they talk. We shouldn't interrupt them while speaking. If we stop them every time they make mistake, they will never learn to say a full sentence. After your student finish you can say that sentence with the same mistake, and ask the student to find that mistake. It will be very helpful. Ask students to repeat the correct form. Sometimes students speak incorrectly because they haven't learned the right grammar to use. Explaining this kind of mistake might take too much time. You don't have to correct it. You can ignore it. Later you can explain the grammar rules once more. One of the best ways to deal with mistakes is to prevent them. Good speakers are also good listeners. Listening and speaking skills depend on each other. Speaking activities are almost always good listening activities. Dealing with common arguments against teaching speaking skills in the classroom Students won't talk or say anything. One way to tackle this problem is to find the root of the problem and start from there. If the problem is cultural, that is in your culture it is unusual for students to talk out loud in class, or if students feel really shy about talking in front of other students then one way to go about breaking this cultural barrier is to create and establish your own classroom culture where speaking out loud in English is the norm. One way to do this is to distinguish your classroom from other classrooms in your school by arranging the classroom desks differently, in groups instead of lines etc. or by decorating the walls in English language and culture posters. From day one teach your students classroom language and keep on teaching it and encourage your students to ask for things and to ask questions in English. Giving positive feedback also helps to encourage and relax shy students to speak more.

Another way to get students motivated to speak more is to allocate a percentage of their final grade to speaking skills and let the students know they are being assessed continually on their speaking practice in class throughout the term. A completely different reason for student silence may simply be that the class activities are boring or are pitched at the wrong level. Very often our interesting communicative speaking activities are not quite as interesting or as communicative as we think they are and all the students are really required to do is answer 'yes' or 'no' which they do quickly and then just sit in silence or worse talking noisily in their L1. So maybe you need to take a closer look at the type of speaking activities you are using and see if they really capture student interest and create a real need for communication. Another way to encourage your students to speak in English is simply to speak in English yourself as much as possible in class. If you are shy

about speaking in English, how can you expect your students to overcome their fears about speaking English? Don't worry if you are not completely fluent or don't have that elusive perfect native accent, as Swain (1985) wrote "We learn to speak by speaking" and that goes for teachers as well as students. The more you practise the more you will improve your own oral skills as well as help your students improve theirs. When students work in pairs or groups they just end up chatting in their own language. Is the activity or task pitched at the right level for the students?

Make sure you give the students all the tools and language they need to be able to complete the task. If the language is pitched too high they may revert to their L1, likewise if the task is too easy they may get bored and revert to their L1. Also, be aware of the fact that some students especially beginners, will often use their L1 as an emotional support at first, translating everything word for word to check they have understood the task before attempting to speak. In the case of these students simply be patient as most likely once their confidence grows in using English their dependence on using their L1 will begin to disappear.

Conclusion. These are just some of the problems that teachers with large classes face when teaching speaking activities in the classroom. These problems are not new nor are the solutions offered above. Teachers all over the world continue to face the same hurdles, but any teacher who has overcome these difficulties and now has a large class of energetic students talking and working in English in groups together will tell you it is worth all the trial and error and effort at the outset.

If you believe in the importance of teaching speaking skills in the classroom but are having difficulties making speaking activities work in your classroom why not contact your local teaching associations or branch of TESOL. Maybe they run workshops for teaching speaking skills, or maybe they can put you in contact with other teachers in similar situations but with more experience teaching speaking skills who will be willing to share their experiences with you.

REFERENCES

1. Исаева У., Джалилова С. The usage of new pedagogical technologies in lessons //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 5. – С. 169-171.
2. Богиева Т. Р. Преимущества и недостатки применения традиционных и нетрадиционных методов преподавания иностранного языка в образовательных учреждениях СПО //Инновационная наука. – 2016. – №. 4-2 (16). – С. 139-141.
3. Mahsudova В. Н. et al. Проблема межкультурной коммуникации в обучении иностранным языкам //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2018. – №. 1. – С. 76-79.

4. Жалилова С. Использование лингвокультурологического подхода в обучении иностранным языкам //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 64-71.
5. Rixsibayevna D. S. TYPES OF LEARNING ENGLISH METHODS IN SPORT DIRECTION //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2024. – Т. 15. – №. 1. – С. 45-49.
6. Rixsibayevna D. S. IMPROVE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 531-534.
7. Rixsibayevna D. S. COMMUNICATIVE-COGNITIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES //World scientific research journal. – 2022. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 198-200.
8. Максудова В. Х., Жалилова С. Р., Нуримова С. Э. КОММУНИКАТИВНО-КОГНИТИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ОБУЧЕНИЮ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ //Путь науки. – 2015. – №. 3. – С. 128-130.
9. Tursunboyeva L. T., Ashirova M. F. Positive teacher-student relations //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 1. – С. 62-66.
10. Tursunboyeva L. T. THE TRANSLATION OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL MATERIALS //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2024. – Т. 15. – №. 1. – С. 41-44.
11. Tursunboyeva L. T. INFLUENCE OF GLOBALIZATION PROCESSES ON STUDENTS //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 35. – №. 6. – С. 83-87
12. Tukhtamuradovna T. L. VARIETY OF METHODS IN TEACHING //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 557-558.
13. Tursunboyeva L. T. INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF A PERSONALITY OF A STUDENT //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 133-140.
14. Рахматова Д. Н. и др. EXPERIMENTAL WORK ON THE ORGANIZATION OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK AND ITS RESULTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 447-454.

15. Керимов Ф. А. и др. ORGANIZATION OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND FAMILY COOPERATION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 463-470.
16. Казоқов Р. Т., Бўриев Б. Ў. МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ВА ОИЛА ҲАМКОРЛИГИДА МАЪНАВИЙ-МАЪРИФИЙ ИШЛАРНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ. – 2024.
17. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. – 2024.
18. Казоқов Р. Т., Джумакулов Ш. Б. ЎЗБЕК КУРАШИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. – 2024.
19. Расулов А. Ф., Казоқов Р. Т. ХОТИН-ҚИЗЛАРНИНГ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯ ВА СПОРТ МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИДА ИШТИРОКИ ВА ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА ЎРНИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 544-551.
20. Казоқов Р., Джўрабаев А., Бўриев Б. Ёш футболчиларнинг техник-тактик тайёргарлигини ҳисобга олган ҳолда ўйин услубини такомиллаштириш //Sport ilmfanining dolzarb muammolari. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 54-56.
21. Cho'lliyev S. I., Yuldasheva K. A., Kazakov R. T. THE IMPORTANCE OF MODELING SPORTS FOR SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 598-901.
22. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
23. Murod o'g'li P. D. MAMLAKATIMIZDA JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTNING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI. – 2023.
24. Achilov O. H. TO INCREASE THE INTEREST OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SPORTS AND TO MAKE THEM REGULARLY ENGAGE IN SPORTS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 218-220.
25. O'G'Li S. O. S., Nurullayev A. Q. THE ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT OF ATHLETICS //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 10-15.
26. O'Imasbek S. MIDDLE LONG DISTANCE RUNNING //BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 10-12.

27. Nurullayev A. Q., Ogli S. U. S. JUDO ACHIEVEMENT AT THE 2021 SPORTS COMPETITION AT THE UNIVERSITY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 234-236.
28. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
29. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
30. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
31. Сафаров Ў. К ВОПРОСАМ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ВУЗОВ НА ОСНОВЕ СИСТЕМНОГО АНАЛИЗА И СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОГО МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
32. Сафаров Ў. МАМЛАКАТИМИЗДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯ ВА СПОРТ СОҲАСИДА ДАВЛАТ-ХУСУСИЙ ШЕРИКЛИК АСОСЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
33. Сафаров Ў. СПОРТ СОҲАСИДА САМАРАЛИ БОШҚАРИШ ТИЗИМИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
34. Сафаров Ў. РОЛЬ СПОРТИВНОГО МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ СПОРТИВНОЙ ИНДУСТРИИ УЗБЕКСКОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
35. Safarov O. O 'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA SPORT MARKETINGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO 'LLARI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
36. Murod o'g'li P. D. MAMLAKATIMIZDA JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTNING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI. – 2023.
37. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
38. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.

39. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
40. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. – 2024.
41. Djurayeva X. X., Xodjiyev R. M., Kazoqov R. T. DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 316-326.
42. Beknazarov S. H. Q., Kazoqov R. T. IDEOLOGICAL THREATS AND IMPORTANT PROBLEMS OF IDEOLOGICAL EDUCATION, NATIONAL HISTORICAL THINKING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1016-1029.
43. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
44. Бойқобилов А. П. и др. ТУРЛИ МАЛАКАЛИ СПОРТЧИЛАР ТОМОНИДАН ЯДРО УЛОҚТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ТАҲЛИЛЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 30-40.
45. Аvezова Г. С., Казоқов Р. Т. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЖАРАЁНИДА ҚЎЛЛАНИЛГАН ТИКЛОВЧИ ВОСИТАЛАРНИ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 205-214.
46. Шопулатов А. Н., Казоқов Р. Т., Хайдарова Г. М. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ БАҲОЛАШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 197-204.
47. Бойқобилов А. П. и др. ТУРЛИ МАЛАКАЛИ СПОРТЧИЛАР ТОМОНИДАН ЯДРО УЛОҚТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ТАҲЛИЛЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 30-40.
48. Yugay L. P. et al. RECOVERY OF THE BODY OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING ATHLETES DURING SPORTS TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 365-371.
49. Akbarov A. et al. ANTHROPOMETRIC-PHYSIOLOGICAL INDICATORS OF MIDDLE-DISTANCE RUNNERS AND RECOVERY OF THEIR BODY DURING TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 358-364.
50. Kim D. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PARTICIPATION OF STUDENT ATHLETES IN THE SWEDISH TEAM AND THE SWEDISH TEAM IN THE

- UZBEKISTAN CHAMPIONSHIP IN HEIGHT ATHLETICS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 346-353.
51. Nurullayeva D. S. et al. ETHICAL PROBLEMS AND THEM IN THE FIELD OF NATURE SOLUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 480-486.
52. Kazaqov R. T., Djo'rabayev A. M. MEANS OF RECOVERY OF WORKING CAPACITY OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 902-911.
53. Kazoqov R. T., Djo'rabayev A. M. DEVELOPMENT OF CYBER SPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 893-901.
54. Yaqubov F. M. et al. METHODOLOGY OF SELECTION OF 10-12-YEAR-OLD PLAYERS AND ORGANIZATION OF TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1271-1279.
55. Казоқов Р. Т. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ЖИСМОНИЙ ВА МАХСУС ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИК КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ //Fan-Sportga. – 2022. – №. 7. – С. 53-55.
56. Гонашвили А. С. и др. Активный досуг узбекской молодежи в аспекте социологического анализа //Теория и практика физической культуры. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 8-8.
57. Baltayeva I. T. et al. USE OF VIRTUAL LABORATORIES TO CONDUCT FOOTBALL TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 709-718.
58. Baltayeva I. T. et al. CREATING AN INFORMATION-EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT USING MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 700-708.
59. Melziddinov R. A., Akramov B. N., Kazaqov R. T. THE RELATIONSHIP OF THE EFFICIENCY OF TECHNICAL-TACTICAL ACTIONS OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS WITH THE LEVEL OF PHYSICAL PREPARATION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1153-1165.
60. Umarov D. X. et al. NATIONAL MOVEMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS'PHYSICAL PREPARATION USING GAMES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 732-741.
61. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.

62. Шопулатов А. Н. Бўлажак мураббийларда жисмоний тарбия ва спорт асосида маънавий қадриятларни ривожлантириш йўллари //Фан-Спортга. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 67-72.
63. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
64. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
65. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. – 2024.